

Short communication

First report of *Rhoptromeris heptoma* (Hymenoptera: Figitidae) for the fauna of Iran

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اولین گزارش *Rhoptromeris heptoma* (Hymenoptera: Figitidae)

برای فون ایران

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چکیده

طی بررسی آفات چغندر در مزارع استان همدان در اوایل آبان سال ۱۳۹۸، پنج نمونه زنبور از خانواده Figitidae از ریشه‌های چغندر قند جمع‌آوری شد. این نمونه‌ها تحت عنوان گونه *Rhoptromeris heptoma* (Hartig, 1840) شناسایی شدند، که برای اولین بار جنس و گونه آن از ایران گزارش می‌شود. این زنبور به عنوان انگل‌واره لارو مگس‌های Chloropidae شناخته شده است.

واژه‌های کلیدی: جدید، زنبور انگل‌واره، چغندر قند، همدان

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Adult wasps (Hymenoptera: Figitidae) emerged from the harvested sugar beet roots from the farmlands of the Hamedan province in October 2019. The figitid wasps appeared in rearing containers from the late October to early November, in a period of 7 - 18 days. Species of the wasps was determined as *Rhoptromeris heptoma* (Hartig, 1840) by the third author of the report. Primary determination was later confirmed by Dr. Mattias Forshage. The genus and species are new records for the fauna of Iran.

The morphological characters of *R. heptoma* was described by Nordlander (1978) and Nordlander & Grijpma (1991) as follows: Metapleura with an anteroventral cavity, posterior margin at most weakly depressed, foveae of pronotal plate separated by a medial bridge, compound eyes and ocelli relatively small, male antenna 13-segmented entirely dark,

flagellomere stout. Femur 2 strongly widened and clearly longer than Femur 1, female club distinctly 7-segmented. Legs relatively short, fore and middle femora expanded mostly in female (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. *Rhoptromeris heptoma* female habitus, lateral view.

Rhoptromeris is widely distributed in the world including Afrotropical region through which most of described species of this genus are known to occur (Quinlan, 1986). *R. heptoma* was also reported from China (Dong & Yang, 1985), Democratic Republic of Congo, South Africa, Austria, British Islands, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands and Ukraine (Baiao & Forshage, 2018).

R. heptoma is known as a koinobiont larval-pupal parasitoid of *Oscinella frit* L. (Diptera: Chloropidae) (Nordlander, 1978). He reported this species in grassy areas and stated that the female adults usually fly over grasses or low-growing vegetation to find hosts. We collected six specimens of the female wasps of *R. heptoma* from sugar beet plants in mid-October in a region of Hamedan near to Juraqan (52° 34'N 48° 32'E, 1730m) with average temperature of 12.5±2°C and 68±5% relative humidity. The chloropid flies were spotted through the same rearing containers of the figitid wasps. According to Nordlander (1978), chloropid flies are the hosts of *R. heptoma*. *R. heptoma* is able to significantly decrease of the fruit flies populations in western Siberia (Chukanova, 1971).

Acknowledgments

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